

FORMATION OF LINGUISTIC AND CULTURAL COMPETENCE IN THE PROCESS OF TEACHING A FOREIGN LANGUAGE

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Abstract. The article contains analysis and the consideration of the content, structural elements and components of the linguo-cultural competence of high school students and the way of forming it in teaching foreign language. Methods of determination the level of the students' competence is based on the results of the formation of the personality's spheres are expounded.

Key words: competence-based education, linguo-cultural competence in academic education, foreign language teaching, the level of the high school students' competence, humanities.

An important indicator of the development and education of a nation is its language. Language is not only the creation of the history of society, but also an active factor in this history: not only the object, but also the subject of history.

At the present stage of the development of society, the cultural function of education is sharply increasing, which turns from a way of transferring knowledge from generation to generation into a way of developing culture, forming a picture of the world and a person's place in it. It is very important to organize the search activity of students in the study of culture through the study of local traditions of English-speaking countries, their traditions and customs, children are included in the environment of folk culture, folklore education introduces children to the origins of national cultures. Modern society, which has entered the era of globalization, urgently needs to understand the linguistic and cultural processes taking place in it. On the one hand, it is necessary to study the language trends that contribute to the "domestication" of nations, on the other hand, the factors of influence of modern culture on the formation of an adequate and necessary kind of key - the "set of literacy", which will contribute to the successful adaptation of a person in society, need to be understood. Considering language as one of the most important values possessed by a nation, since it reflects those spiritual and material, significant and important objects, norms and laws, ways of communication, which are the key principles of the development of any individual, we define linguistic and cultural competence as the inner wealth of the individual, formed through the knowledge, development of the fundamental knowledge of society. Each student individually, and our entire state as a whole, is interested today in the practical mastery of a foreign language, ensuring familiarization with world culture. Without the awareness and development of language culture, linguistic and cultural competence cannot be formed, and without the formation of linguistic and cultural competence, it is impossible to master language culture. We believe that the central idea is the interconnected study of language and culture, the formation of linguistic and cultural competence. It is about mastering and understanding basic knowledge from the perspective of the relationship between language and culture, which involves: understanding the basic linguistic and cultural units of native speakers, their cultural content, their place in the linguistic picture of the world; mastering the basic linguistic and cultural units of native speakers, closely related to the history, culture,

lifestyle, customs and mentality of the people who created them; actualization of the basic linguistic and cultural units of native speakers in the socio-cultural situation.

-cultural competence (possession of culturally-determined norms), which in turn includes: socio-cultural competence (knowledge of the norms, rules and traditions of their society);

- inter-sociocultural competence (knowledge of the norms, rules and traditions of another society).

In this interpretation, the concept of linguistic and cultural competence will mean not only the knowledge of a certain number of words and expressions, but also a full awareness and understanding of the entire complex of cultural processes that accompany and determine the meaning of these linguistic units and will contribute to the successful interaction of the individual with other members of society and its self-realization in this society. One of the goals of teaching a foreign language is the development of foreign language communicative competence, therefore, the main purpose of teaching a foreign language is to form communicative competence, i.e. the ability and willingness to carry out foreign language interpersonal and intercultural communication with native speakers. Modern schoolchildren have the opportunity to learn a foreign language and at the same time develop their communicative competence. The leading component in the communicative competence is speech (communication) skills, which are formed on the basis of: language skills; linguistic and country-specific knowledge.

The communicative competence includes the following essential skills: to read and understand simple, authentic texts (with an understanding of the main content and with full understanding); to communicate verbally in standard situations in the educational, labor, cultural, household sphere; to verbally briefly tell about yourself, the environment, to retell, express an opinion, an assessment; the ability to formalize and convey elementary information in writing (writing). This is how the minimum level of communicative competence is defined in the state educational standard for foreign languages. Foreign language communicative competence is a certain level of proficiency in language, speech and socio-cultural knowledge, skills and abilities, which allows the learner to vary their speech behavior in a communicative acceptable and appropriate way depending on the communication situation. Foreign language communicative competence has a complex structure and includes a number of competencies:

1. Linguistic competence is one of the main components of communicative competence. Its content is the ability of a person to correctly construct grammatical forms and syntactic constructions in accordance with the norms of a particular language. Linguistic competence as one of the main components of communicative competence is divided into language and speech competence. Language competence is knowledge in the field of the language system (within the program minimum), skills of operating with this knowledge. Speech competence- possession of the norm of speech behavior (in all types of speech activity).

Educational competence is the ability and readiness of a person to effectively carry out educational activities when mastering a foreign language as an academic subject. The importance of learning competence for students:

- organizes and optimizes students' independent work on the language;
- reduces time, physical and mental costs when working on a foreign language;
- improves the quality of mastering foreign language communication;

- increases interest in the subject.

2. Compensatory competence - the ability to overcome difficulties in generating foreign language utterances, i.e. its formation involves the development of the ability and willingness to overcome the deficit of their foreign language knowledge, skills and abilities.

The value of compensatory competence:

- allows you to overcome the inevitable difficulties

associated with ignorance of language units, with a lack of understanding of language, socio-cultural units;

- liberates, allows you to remove the language barrier;

- develops his own communicative competence in his native language.

3. Sociocultural competence — the ability to build speech and non-speech behavior taking into account the norms of societies that speak the language being studied.

The importance of socio-cultural competence:

- knowledge of the national mentality, the picture of the world;

- removal of cultural difficulties;

- awareness of the expansion of one's own worldview, ideas about a different socio-cultural community.

Socio-cultural competence is divided into the following types:

1. Sociolinguistic competence involves the ability to choose the linguistic form and method of language expression that is adequate to the conditions of the act of communication, i.e. the communication situation, goals and intentions, and social roles of communication partners.

2. Cultural competence consists in mastering the national and cultural specifics of the country of the language being studied and the ability to build their speech and non-speech behavior in accordance with this specificity. It involves mastering information about the country, the language being studied, its geographical location, natural conditions, sights, the state structure, the national peculiarities of life and culture of the country of the language being studied, the peculiarities of speech and non-speech behavior of native speakers of a foreign language. The formation of linguistic and cultural competence is realized in the selection of linguistic and cultural material according to the concept sphere relevant for schoolchildren and the main concepts; in the application of all types of speech activity for the formation of linguistic and cultural competence of receptive and productive types at the main and final stages of training; in the creation of the concept of linguistic and cultural manuals, in the justification of special texts and tasks for them, which are aimed at the formation of linguistic and cultural competence and its control.

The main unit of linguistic and cultural information, the method of its presentation and consolidation is the text, which includes concepts related to the main concepts. The formation of linguistic and cultural competence can be carried out on the basis of texts of different types and genres.

The text, in turn, acts as a universal component for explaining the specific content of concepts, since the text, modeling situations, corrects the shades of the meaning of the word and carries valuable cultural information. In such circumstances, the text is the basis and at the same time the mechanism for the formation of linguistic and cultural competence.

Conclusion:

Thus, communicative competence is an integrative concept that includes both the skills and abilities to perform actions with language material, and country-specific knowledge, skills and abilities. Knowledge, skills, skills of only one part can not indicate the training in communication, i.e. the reception and transmission of information through different types of speech activity. Therefore, in relation to the specifics of the educational subject "foreign language", the concept of learning means the acquisition by students of a particular level of communicative competence.

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